
Supplementary material for: Cyclic Action Graphs for Goal Recognition Problems with Inaccurately Initialised Fluents

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Modifications Made to the Initial State

In our paper, we present the results of running our GR approach on a dataset containing problems with inaccurate initial states. The initial states were made inaccurate by setting fluents to incorrect values, i.e., by modifying which atoms (that can be deleted/added by actions) appear in the PDDL defined initial state. A list of what predicates can be changed (when grounded) is provided in Table 1. In this table, if a grounding of predicate 1 is mentioned in the initial state, it can be changed to a grounding of predicate 2. If not, if predicate 2 is mentioned in the initial state, it can be changed to predicate 1. If neither are mentioned (i.e., both are false), all groundings (i.e., possible object combinations) of predicate 1 (i.e., the true predicate) could be inserted into the initial state.

For example, in an Easy-IPC-Grid problem, if `(at-robot 1.0)` is mentioned in the initial state, it can be replaced by any other grounding of the `(at-robot ?2)` predicate. Which grounding it is replaced by is selected at random. Moreover, in this problem, several locations will be listed as locked (e.g., `(locked 1.0)` and `(locked 2.0)`); these atoms can be replaced by `(open 1.0)` and `(open 2.0)`. In the original Easy-IPC-Grid problems, the `(carrying ?1)` predicate is not mentioned in the initial state; thus, every possible grounding of this predicate could be inserted, e.g., `(carrying key1)` and `(carrying key2)`. Therefore, there are 5 fluents, i.e., `(at-robot 1.0)`, `(locked 1.0)`, `(locked 2.0)`, `(not (carrying key1))` and `(not (carrying key2))`, whose value can be changed.

Table 1: Predicates whose groundings in the initial state were modified to create an inaccurate initial state.

Domain	Predicate 1	Predicate 2
Blocks-World	(HANDEMPY)	(HOLDING ?1 - block)
	(CLEAR ?1 - block)	(not (CLEAR ?1 - block))
	(ONTABLE ?1 - block)	(not (ONTABLE ?1 - block)) or (ON ?1 - block ?2 - block)
	(ON ?1 - block ?2 - block)	(not (ON ?1 - block ?2 - block)) or (ON ?1 - block ?3 - block) or (ONTABLE ?1 - block)
Campus	(at ?1 - place)	(at ?2 - place)
	(banking)	(not (banking))
	(lecture-1-taken)	(not (lecture-1-taken))
	(lecture-2-taken)	(not (lecture-2-taken))
	(lecture-3-taken)	(not (lecture-3-taken))
	(lecture-4-taken)	(not (lecture-4-taken))
	(group-meeting-1)	(not (group-meeting-1))
	(group-meeting-2)	(not (group-meeting-2))
	(group-meeting-3)	(not (group-meeting-3))
	(coffee)	(not (coffee))
(breakfast)	(not (breakfast))	
(lunch)	(not (lunch))	
Depots	(at ?1 - Truck ?2 - Depot) or (at ?1 - Truck ?3 - Distributor)	(at ?1 - Truck ?4 - Depot) or (at ?1 - Truck ?5 - Distributor)
	(at ?1 - Crate ?2 - Depot) or (at ?1 - Crate ?3 - Distributor)	(at ?1 - Crate ?4 - Depot) or (at ?1 - Crate ?5 - Distributor)
	(at ?1 - Hoist ?2 - Depot) or (at ?1 - Hoist ?3 - Distributor)	(at ?1 - Hoist ?4 - Depot) or (at ?1 - Hoist ?5 - Distributor)
	(on ?1 - Crate ?2 - Crate) or (on ?1 - Crate ?3 - Pallet) or (in ?1 - Crate ?4 - Truck)	(on ?1 - Crate ?5 - Crate) or (on ?1 - Crate ?6 - Pallet) or (in ?1 - Crate ?7 - Truck) or None
	(clear ?1 - Pallet)	(not (clear ?1 - Pallet))
	(clear ?1 - Crate)	(not (clear ?1 - Crate))
	(lifting ?1 - Hoist ?2 - Crate) or (available ?1 - Hoist)	(available ?1 - Hoist) or (and (lifting ?1 - Hoist ?3 - Crate) (not (available ?1 - Hoist)))
Driverlog	(((at ?1 ?2) if (and (OBJ ?1) (LOCATION ?2))) or ((in ?1 ?2) if (and (OBJ ?1) (TRUCK ?3))))	(((at ?1 ?4) if (and (OBJ ?1) (LOCATION ?4))) or ((in ?1 ?5) if (and (OBJ ?1) (TRUCK ?5))))
	(at ?1 ?2) if (and (TRUCK ?1) (LOCATION ?2))	(at ?1 ?3) if (and (TRUCK ?1) (LOCATION ?3))
	(at ?1 ?2) if (and (DRIVER ?1) (LOCATION ?2))	(at ?1 ?3) if (and (DRIVER ?1) (LOCATION ?3))
	(empty ?1) if (TRUCK ?1)	(not (empty ?1)) if (TRUCK ?1)
	(driving ?1 ?2) if (and (DRIVER ?1) (TRUCK ?2))	(driving ?1 ?3) if (and (DRIVER ?1) (TRUCK ?3))
(at ?1 - robot ?2 - location)	((at ?1 - robot ?3 - location)(occupied ?3 location)(not (occupied ?2 location)))	
DWR	(unloaded ?1 - robot) or (loaded ?1 - robot ?2 - container)	(loaded ?1 - robot ?3 - container) or (unloaded ?1 - robot)
	(empty ?1 - crane) or (holding ?1 - crane ?2 - container)	(holding ?1 - crane ?3 - container) or (empty ?1 - crane)
	(in ?1 - container ?2 pile)	(in ?1 - container ?3 pile)
	(top ?1 - container ?2 pile)	(top ?3 - container ?2 pile)
	(on ?1 - container ?2 container)	(on ?1 - container ?3 container)
Easy-IPC-Grid	(at-robot ?1 - place)	(at-robot ?2 - place)
	(locked ?1 - place)	(open ?1 - place)
	(carrying ?1 - key)	(not (carrying ?1 - key))
Ferry	(at-ferry ?1) if (location ?1)	(at-ferry ?2) if (location ?2)
	(((at ?1 ?2) if (and (car ?1) (location ?2))) or ((on ?1) if (car ?1)))	(((at ?1 ?4) if (and (car ?1) (location ?4))) or (((and (on ?1) (not (empty-ferry))) if (car ?1))
Intrusion-Detection	(recon-performed ?1 - host)	(not (recon-performed ?1 - host))
	(broke-into ?1 - host)	(not (broke-into ?1 - host))
	(deleted-logs ?1 - host)	(not (deleted-logs ?1 - host))
	(modified-files ?1 - host)	(not (modified-files ?1 - host))
	(access-obtained ?1 - host)	(not (access-obtained ?1 - host))
	(root-access-obtained ?1 - host)	(not (root-access-obtained ?1 - host))
	(files-downloaded ?1 - host)	(not (files-downloaded ?1 - host))
	(information-gathered ?1 - host)	(not (information-gathered ?1 - host))
	(vandalized ?1 - host)	(not (vandalized ?1 - host))
	(data-stolen-from ?1 - host)	(not (data-stolen-from ?1 - host))

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Domain	Predicate 1	Predicate 2
Kitchen	(taken ?1 - object)	(not (taken ?1 - object))
	(used ?1 - useable)	(not (used ?1 - useable))
	(water_boiled)	(not (water_boiled))
	(made_tea)	(not (made_tea))
	(made_cereals)	(not (made_cereals))
	(lunch_packed)	(not (lunch_packed))
	(made_breakfast)	(not (made_breakfast))
	(made_salad)	(not (made_salad))
	(made_coffee)	(not (made_coffee))
	(made_cheese_sandwich)	(not (made_cheese_sandwich))
	(made_toast)	(not (made_toast))
	(made_buttered_toast)	(not (made_buttered_toast))
	(made_peanut_butter_sandwich)	(not (made_peanut_butter_sandwich))
(made_dinner)	(not (made_dinner))	
Logistics	(at ?1 - package ?2 - airport) or (at ?1 - package ?3 - location) or (in ?1 - package ?4 - airplane) or (in ?1 - package ?5 - truck)	(at ?1 - package ?6 - airport) or (at ?1 - package ?7 - location) or (in ?1 - package ?8 - airplane) or (in ?1 - package ?9 - truck)
	(at ?1 - truck ?2 - airport) or (at ?1 - truck ?3 - location) or (at ?1 - airplane ?2 - airport)	(at ?1 - truck ?4 - airport) or (at ?1 - truck ?5 - location) or (at ?1 - airplane ?3 - airport)
Miconic	(boarded ?1) if (passenger ?1)	(not (boarded ?1)) if (passenger ?1)
	(served ?1) if (passenger ?1)	(not (served ?1)) if (passenger ?1)
Rovers	(lift-at ?1) if (floor ?1)	(lift-at ?2) if (floor ?2)
	(at ?1 ?2) if (and (rover ?1)(waypoint ?2))	(at ?1 ?3) if (and (rover ?1)(waypoint ?3))
	(empty ?1) if (store ?1)	(full ?1) if (store ?1)
	(not (have_rock_analysis ?1 ?2)) if (and (rover ?1)(waypoint ?2)(at_rock_sample ?2))	(and (have_rock_analysis ?3 ?2) (not (at_rock_sample ?2))) if (and (rover ?3)(waypoint ?2))
	(not (have_soil_analysis ?1 ?2)) if (and (rover ?1)(waypoint ?2)(at_soil_sample ?2))	(and (have_soil_analysis ?3 ?2) (not (at_soil_sample ?2))) if (and (rover ?3)(waypoint ?2))
	(not (calibrated ?1 ?2)) if (and (camera ?1)(rover ?2)(equipped_for_imaging ?2))	(calibrated ?1 ?2) if (camera ?1)(rover ?2)(equipped_for_imaging ?2)
	(available ?1) if (rover ?1)	(not (available ?1)) if (rover ?1)
	(not (have_image ?1 ?2 ?3)) if (and (rover ?1)(objective ?2)(mode ?3)(equipped_for_imaging ?1))	(have_image ?4 ?2 ?3) if (and (rover ?4)(objective ?2)(mode ?3))
	(communicated_soil_data ?1) if (and (waypoint ?1)(at_soil_sample ?1))	(not (communicated_soil_data ?1)) if (and (waypoint ?1)(at_soil_sample ?1))
	(communicated_rock_data ?1) if (and (waypoint ?1)(at_rock_sample ?1))	(not (communicated_rock_data ?1)) if (and (waypoint ?1)(at_rock_sample ?1))
(communicated_image_data ?1 ?2) if (and (objective ?1)(mode ?2))	(not (communicated_image_data ?1 ?2)) if (and (objective ?1)(mode ?2))	
(channel_free ?1) if (lander ?1)	(not (channel_free ?1)) if (lander ?1)	
(pointing ?1 ?2) if (and (satellite ?1)(direction ?2))	(pointing ?1 ?3) if (and (satellite ?1)(direction ?3))	
Satellite	(power_avail ?1) if (satellite ?1)	(not (power_avail ?1)) if (satellite ?1)
	(power_on ?1) if (instrument ?1)	(not (power_on ?1)) if (instrument ?1)
	(calibrated ?1) if (instrument ?1)	(not (calibrated ?1)) if (instrument ?1)
	(have_image ?1 ?2) if (and (direction ?1)(mode ?2))	(not (have_image ?1 ?2)) if (and (direction ?1)(mode ?2))
	(at-robot ?1 - LOC)	(at-robot ?2 - LOC)
Sokoban	(at ?1 - BOX ?2 - LOC)	(at ?1 - BOX ?3 - LOC) (clear ?2 - LOC) (not (clear ?3 - LOC))
	((at ?1 ?2) if (and (person ?1)(city ?2))) or ((in ?1 ?3) if (and (person ?1)(aircraft ?3)))	((at ?1 ?4) if (and (person ?1)(city ?4))) or ((in ?1 ?5) if (and (person ?1)(aircraft ?5)))
Zeno-travel	(at ?1 ?2) if (and (aircraft ?1)(city ?2))	(at ?1 ?3) if (and (aircraft ?1)(city ?3))
	(fuellevel ?1 ?2) if (and (aircraft ?1)(flevel ?2))	(fuellevel ?1 ?3) if (and (aircraft ?1)(flevel ?3))